

Cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity among children and adolescents: a scoping review protocol

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Abstract

Introduction

Cyberbullying represents a major public health concern due to short- and long-term negative consequences for young people and societies. Ethnic minorities and indigenous people may represent particularly vulnerable populations for cyberbullying involvement. The scarce existing literature is characterized by conceptual confusion and methodological heterogeneity, leading to the need for a scoping review to map research in this area. The present protocol is for a systematic scoping review, the objective of which is to provide an overview of the state of the art of empirical research worldwide on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity among young people, by summarizing aspects of conceptualization, methodology, and results.

Methods and Analysis

The scoping review will be carried out in accordance with JBI guidelines for conducting scoping reviews and results will be reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews. The following databases will be searched for study selection: Academic Search Premier, ERIC, PsychINFO (OVID), PubMed, Scopus, SocINDEX, Web of Science, Medline, Proquest. The review will include peer-reviewed studies considering at least children and adolescents aged between 6 and 18 years old belonging to an ethnic minority or indigenous group, reporting data on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity, and published in English. Two researchers will independently screen citations for title and abstract first, and for full-texts after. Pilot screenings before each phase will be undertaken to calibrate screening between researchers. Data extraction will be conducted independently by two researchers, after piloting the extraction tool.

Ethics and Dissemination

This scoping review is part of the PARTICIPATE project, that has received funding from the European Union HORIZON-MSCA-2021 Doctoral Networks Programme under Grant Agreement no. 101073332. Findings of this work will be disseminated through a peer-reviewed publication and participation at scientific conferences.

Keywords: ethnic-racial identity; indigenous; migrants; online bullying; youths.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background and rationale

Cyberbullying has been recognized as a public health concern leading to short- and long-term negative psychosocial and physical consequences on young people and has a detrimental impact on groups and society

as well (UNESCO, 2019). Although research has not agreed on a shared definition of the phenomenon, the one proposed by Smith et al. (2008) provides a currently widely recognized conceptualization, according to which cyberbullying refers to “*an aggressive, intentional act carried out by a group or individual, using electronic forms of contact, repeatedly and over time against a victim who cannot easily defend him or herself*”.

Ethnic minority and indigenous children and adolescents may represent populations particularly sensitive to negative developmental trajectories after exposure to risk factors, such as cyber-victimization or perpetration (Carlson & Frazer, 2018; Özdemir et al., 2018). *Ethnic minority* represents an umbrella term to refer to different kinds of groups of individuals from disadvantaged social positions at a national level due to their ethnic-racial social identity (migrants, racial groups, refugees and national minorities), in comparison to the majority population holding a dominant social position in a specific country (Johnson et al., 2019). *Indigenous*, instead, are people with historical connection to a region, because originally inhabiting specific lands prior to colonization (Williams & Schertzer, 2019). Self-identification of indigeneity and strong willingness of maintaining and transmitting their own identity and lands represent focal characteristics of indigenous groups (Sarivaara et al., 2013). While indigenous populations have been mostly overlooked in the cyberbullying field, they might undergo different experiences due to various contextual, cultural and policy factors (Carlson & Frazer 2018). For example, Sámi people in Norway benefit from specific recognized rights that other minorities, such as migrants, do not have, leading Sámi to cover a more powerful social position; however, they have also suffered persistent assimilation policies that can still have discrimination consequences (Hansen, 2022). Thus, taking into consideration differences among various ethnic groups is of paramount importance to understand the cyberbullying phenomenon.

Research has started to focus more on (cyber)bullying related to ethnicity due to the consistent increase of the phenomenon of international migration which, leading to higher level of multiculturalism in societies and schools, has an effect on youths’ development (Fandrem et al., 2021; Pyżalski & Smith, 2022). Two lines of research have emerged in the literature. The first one, which most of the studies refer to, has investigated cyberbullying involving ethnic minorities either as victims or perpetrators, without the motivation behind the cyberbullying behavior being necessarily related to ethnicity. This body of research mainly focused on detecting differences in prevalence rates or motives of (cyber)bullying involvement *between* ethnic minority and majority groups. Research has suggested that there might be distinctive cyberbullying involvement dynamics among children and adolescents belonging to different ethnic groups, drawing the attention to deeper investigate these differences (Llorent et al., 2016; Solomontos-Kountouri & Strohmeier, 2021). More recently, a second line of research has developed focusing on ethnicity-based cyberbullying, which occurs when victims are explicitly targeted because of their ethnicity. Different terms have been used in literature to refer to this phenomenon, such as prejudice-, stigma-, bias-, identity-, and racist-based (cyber)bullying. Also the measurement for identifying this kind of bullying differs (Pyżalski & Smith, 2022).

For the purpose of the current work, we will use the overarching expression *cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity* to comprehend both ethnic minority and indigenous groups involved in cyberbullying, since ethnicity and indigeneity are the two focal identity aspects taken into consideration by the present review. Moreover, we will refer to the two aforementioned lines of research as investigations of *cyberbullying involving ethnic minorities or indigenous people* and *cyberbullying based on ethnic or indigenous identity*, respectively.

More research is available on offline bullying based on ethnicity, than cyberbullying, showing migrant youths to be more at risk for this kind of face-to-face victimization than their majority peers (Broll et al., 2018; Caravita et al., 2020). The very few studies that explored cyberbullying among migrant students (Schultze-Krumbholz et al., 2022; Zych et al., 2023), national minorities (Pazhouhi, 2023; Zych et al., 2023), and Indigenous Australians (Carlson & Frazer, 2018) suggested that ethnic minority or indigenous youths are cyber-victimized because of their ethnic or indigenous identity at significantly higher degrees than their majority peers. Evidence also suggested that identity-based bullying seems to be more commonly spread in

cyberspace than in real life settings (Earnshaw et al., 2018) and may lead to even greater negative consequences than non-identity-based cyberbullying (Pyzalski & Smith, 2022).

Recently, relevant reviews considering cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity have been published. For example, Sciacca and colleagues (2023) carried out a systematic review on mental health consequences of cybervictimization, Vandebosch and colleagues (2022) conducted a scoping review on technological interventions to address peer-aggression (including cyberbullying), while Carlson and Frazer (2018) published a narrative review on cyberbullying among Indigenous Australian. However, to our knowledge no systematic scoping review has been conducted to summarize the literature collected worldwide distinguishing cyberbullying involving ethnic minority or indigenous young people and cyberbullying based on ethnic or indigenous identity.

To sum up, literature on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity is still scarce, methodologically heterogeneous, and often characterized by a conceptual confusion that needs to be solved, more specifically distinguishing cyberbullying *based* on ethnic or indigenous identity from the phenomenon of cyberbullying *involving* ethnic minorities or indigenous people (Caravita et al., 2020; Palladino et al., 2020). The need of mapping where research has arrived so far in the field of cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity is therefore evident. Thus, the present work aims to fill this gap with a systematic scoping review that will provide insights for the future research agenda, highlighting research gaps, providing a clearer conceptualization of the phenomenon of cyberbullying based on ethnic or indigenous identity distinct from cyberbullying involving ethnic minorities or indigenous people, identifying theoretical and methodological limitations, and providing useful suggestions for improvement in this regard.

1.2 Objective and review questions

The present protocol is for a systematic scoping review that aims at providing an overview of the state of the art of empirical research worldwide on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity involving ethnic minority (migrants, racial groups, refugees or national minorities) or indigenous children and adolescents, by summarizing aspects of conceptualization, methodology, and results across studies. Findings of this scoping review will contribute to develop a better overview of the phenomenon of cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity and will inform policy and future research agenda. The research questions are as follow:

- 1) What are the characteristics of studies on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity in terms of which ethnic minorities or indigenous groups have been addressed and what types of contexts have been considered?
- 2) What theoretical approaches have been adopted and what definitions have been described to study cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity?
- 3) What methodological approaches have been used and what variables have been observed as antecedents and outcomes of cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity?
- 4) What kind of prevention and intervention actions have been implemented?

2. Methods

Conducting a scoping review represents the most appropriate method to address the aim of the current work because it allows to provide a comprehensive overview on the topic of interest (Peters et al., 2020a). The review will be carried out in accordance with JBI guidelines for conducting scoping reviews drawn up by Peters and colleagues (2020a). JBI manual guided the compilation of the current protocol as well (Peters et al., 2020a). The template elaborated by Lely and colleagues (2023) was chosen to write the present protocol, because specifically developed to provide a detailed and extensive protocol for conducting a scoping review. The present protocol will be registered with the Open Science Framework (OSF). As recommended by Peters and colleagues (2020b), the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR; Tricco et al., 2018) will be used to report the final scoping review.

2.1 Eligibility criteria

Eligibility criteria of the review have been formulated in accordance with the Participants, Concept, Context and Types of evidence sources framework of the JBI guidelines (Peters et al., 2020a). Preliminary searches have been undertaken to inform eligibility criteria, whose development represents an iterative process, and therefore, can be subjected to modifications. Table 1 summarizes the inclusion and exclusion criteria that will be applied to carry out the study selection.

Table 1. Summary of eligibility criteria that will be applied to identified citations

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	<p>Children and adolescents aged 6-18 (from 1st to 13th grade in school).</p> <p>Studies should include participants from an ethnic minority or indigenous group.</p> <p>Ethnic minority can be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - International migrants: people moving from their usual country of residence (United Nations, 1998); both first generation and second generation migrants (e.g., national citizenship, with at least one parent from abroad) - Racial groups: people who belong to a group based on physical characteristics such as the skin color (Johnson et al., 2019) - Refugees: people outside the country of their nationality (or not having a nationality) and unable or unwilling to return to that country due to founded fear of being persecuted (UNHCR, 2010) - National minorities: groups characterized by a long-lasting affiliation to a country (e.g., Roma people in Norway) (Ministry of Local Government and Modernisation, 2020). <p>Examples of Indigenous groups are Sámi in Norway or Māori in New Zealand.</p>	<p>Children below 6 years old and people above 18 years old.</p> <p>No ethnic minority or indigenous participants have been involved in the study.</p>
Concept	<p>There must be data on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity (general cyberbullying involving ethnic minorities or indigenous people and cyberbullying based on ethnic or indigenous identity).</p>	<p>No data on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity have been reported (e.g., the role of ethnicity, migrant background,</p>

		indigeneity, race in cyberbullying cases). Studies focused on other typologies of cyber-aggression or only on offline bullying.
Context	Studies conducted worldwide.	None.
Types of evidence sources	Empirical primary studies (qualitative, quantitative, mixed-method, all kinds of study designs).	Systematic reviews (including scoping reviews), meta-analyses, reports, conceptual papers.
Language	English.	Languages other than English.
Publication type	Scientific peer-reviewed articles.	Not peer-reviewed articles.

2.1.1 Participants

This scoping review will consider studies involving children and adolescents aged between 6 and 18 years old belonging to an ethnic minority group (i.e., migrants, racial groups, refugees, national minorities) or an indigenous group (e.g., Sámi), which represent particularly vulnerable populations. The impact of cyberbullying, in fact, can be more damaging to youths than to adults (Peguero & Hong, 2020). Moreover, ethnic minority and indigenous youths may be more at risk for cyberbullying victimization (Peguero & Hong, 2020) or perpetration (Solomontos-Kountouri & Strohmeier, 2021), and for developing even greater negative consequences than majority youths (Sciacca et al., 2023). Studies that include only ethnic minority or indigenous youths will be included, as well as those that include both an ethnic minority/indigenous group and majority children and adolescents. Instead, studies that include participants outside the eligible age range or involving exclusively participants belonging to a majority ethnic group will be excluded.

2.1.2 Concept

This scoping review will focus on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity as an overarching concept, which includes two different forms of the phenomenon. The first one refers to general cyberbullying involving ethnic minorities or indigenous people either as victims or perpetrators, but the motivation behind the cyberbullying behavior is not necessarily related to ethnicity/indigeneity. The second one refers to cyberbullying based on ethnic or indigenous identity that takes place when victims are explicitly targeted *because* of their ethnicity/indigeneity (Pyżalski & Smith, 2022). Studies will be included when they focus on either one of the two forms of cyberbullying. When they do not primarily focus on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity, studies will still be considered eligible when they report data on the relationship between ethnicity/indigeneity and cyberbullying.

2.1.3 Context

No restriction will be applied regarding the geographical area or the period of investigation. The present scoping review, in fact, aims at providing the most comprehensive overview as possible on the phenomenon of interest worldwide. Cultural and social context plays a crucial role in the conceptualization, analysis, and interpretation of data and will therefore be coded.

2.1.4 Types of evidence sources

The scoping review will include empirical studies with no restrictions on the methodology or study design adopted. Therefore, qualitative, quantitative, mixed-method studies as well as all typologies of study designs (e.g., cross-sectional, longitudinal, prospective, retrospective, experimental/quasi-experimental, randomized

controlled trials, single-case series studies) will be considered eligible. On the other hand, systematic reviews (including scoping reviews), meta-analyses, reports, and conceptual papers will be excluded; however, their reference lists will be examined to identify possible primary studies not detected through the search. Only articles written in English will be included to have at least two reviewers understanding the language of the papers. Finally, only peer-reviewed published articles will be considered eligible, since the interest of the scoping review is to summarize characteristics of the published literature on the topic.

2.2 Information sources and search strategy

The search strategy has been developed by the review team. A specialist librarian peer-reviewed the search strategy. Two experts were consulted in validating the search string. A preliminary search was undertaken to discover relevant papers on the topic and to identify possible search terms. The final search string, presented in table 2, includes terms related to the three main concepts of the review: children and adolescents, ethnicity/indigeneity, and cyberbullying. Each concept has been expanded using synonyms. Truncation and Boolean operators to combine terms will be employed according to the rules of each database. The string has been piloted and the final search will be performed in the following databases: Academic Search Premier, ERIC, PsychINFO (OVID), PubMed, Scopus, SocINDEX, Web of Science, Medline, Proquest. The listed databases have been selected because they specifically cover the area of interest of the current scoping review. Moreover, reference lists from existing related reviews and from included papers that pass full-text phase will be screened. EPPI-Reviewer will be used for citation management.

Table 2. Search terms related to the main concepts

Concept	Search terms
Children and adolescents	child* OR kid OR kids OR pupil* OR boy* OR girl* OR adolescent* OR preadolescen* OR “pre adolescen*” OR teen* OR preteen* OR “pre teen*” OR minor OR minors OR youth* OR young* OR student* OR school* OR peer*
Ethnicity/indigeneity	ethnic* OR minorit* OR race* OR raci* OR immigra* OR migra* OR refugee* OR indigen* OR aborigin* OR Native* OR “First Nation*” OR Inuit OR Métis OR Aymara OR Quechua OR “Pacific Islander*” OR “Torres Strait Island*” OR Māori OR Polynesian* OR Sámi OR Roma* OR Sinti OR nationalit* OR prejudice* OR identity OR “bias* based” OR “stigma based” OR “culture based” OR multicultur* OR “multi cultur*” OR multiethnic* OR multirace* OR multiraci*
Cyberbullying	cyberbully* OR cyberbullies OR “cyber bully*” OR “cyber bullies” OR cyberperpetrat* OR “cyber perpetrat*” OR cybervictim* OR “cyber victim*” OR cyberharas* OR “cyber haras*” OR cyberaggres* OR “cyber aggres*” OR cyberbystander* OR “cyber bystander*” OR “cyber discrimination” OR “cyber hate” OR “cyber prejudice*” OR “cyber racism” OR “online bully*” OR “on-line bully*” OR “online bullies” OR “on-line bullies” OR “online perpetrat*” OR “on-line perpetrat*” OR “online victim*” OR “on-line victim*” OR “online haras*” OR “on-line haras*” OR “online aggres*” OR “on-line aggres*” OR “online discrimination” OR “on-line discrimination” OR “online hate” OR “on-line hate” OR “online prejudice*” OR “on-line prejudice” OR “online racism” OR “on-line racism” OR “digital bully*” OR “digital bullies” OR “digital haras*” OR “digital aggres*” OR “internet bully*” OR “internet bullies*” OR “internet victim*” OR “internet haras*” OR “electronic bully*” OR “electronic bullies” OR “electronic victim*” OR “electronic haras*” OR “virtual bull*” OR “virtual victim*” OR “virtual haras*” OR “virtual aggres*” OR “social media bully*” OR “technology facilitated violence”

2.3 Study selection

Identified citations will be uploaded in EPPI-Reviewer and duplicates will be removed. A two-stage independent screening of records will be conducted by two researchers in accordance with the eligibility criteria. First, the two independent reviewers will screen articles for titles and abstracts for assuring inter-rater reliability. In case of disagreement, the researchers will discuss to achieve a unanimous decision, or a third researcher will be involved. Second, full-texts of included studies will be retrieved and screened, always in accordance with the eligibility criteria. Also in this case, disagreement will be handled through discussion or involving a third researcher. In order to ensure consensus among the reviewers about eligibility criteria understanding, a trial titles and abstracts screening will be conducted by all the team members with the first 10% of citations and then discussed among the researchers for calibration and validation purposes. The same procedure will be adopted before starting the full-texts screening. The results of the study selection process will be presented with the PRISMA flow diagram (Tricco et al., 2018).

2.4 Data extraction

Data will be double coded by independent reviewers, using a data extraction tool that will be developed by researchers based on the research questions and following JBI guidelines (Peters et al., 2020a). A pilot data extraction will be performed by all the reviewers independently from the 10% of included articles. Reviewers will then meet to assess consistency in the extraction and to update the tool. As data extraction process will be iterative, the extraction tool will be revised and modified throughout the process if necessary. Draft of data extraction tools are provided and divided for quantitative (table 3) and qualitative studies (table 4). Any disagreement between reviewers will be solved through discussion or involving a third reviewer. Authors of included papers will be contacted for missing data twice: if no answer is received after the first contact within two weeks, researchers will contact authors a second time. If the missing information is not retrieved, it will be coded as “Not Reported”. Tables for summarizing extracted data will be produced.

Table 3. Draft of data extraction tool for quantitative studies

Authors and year	Country	Study aims	Theoretical framework	Type of context	Population				Cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity			
					Sample size	Age range and mean	Gender	Ethnicity/Indigeneity	Definition used	Roles studied	Instruments used	Prevalence rate
Antecedents		Moderator/ mediators		Consequences				Interventions				
Variables considered	Instruments used	Variables considered	Instruments used	Variables considered	Instruments used	Name and aims	Main characteristics	Effectiveness				

Table 4. Draft of data extraction tool for qualitative studies

Authors and year	Country	Study aims	Theoretical framework	Study design	Population			
					Sample size	Age range and mean	Gender	Ethnicity/Indigeneity
Cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity definition	Instruments used for data collection	Main results						

2.5 Synthesis of results

Results from study selection process will be displayed with a PRISMA flow diagram showing included and excluded articles (Tricco et al., 2018). Extracted data will be presented through tables, that will be developed from data extraction tools presented in tables 3 and 4. A narrative summary will also be provided to describe the observed phenomenon and variables across studies. A summary of knowledge gaps will be provided and recommendations based on the findings of the present scoping review and targeted to researchers and policy makers, will be given. It is expected that the plan for synthesis and presentation of results may be subject to change once arrived at this stage of the review.

2.6 Ethics and dissemination

Since the present scoping review will synthesize information from available publications, no ethical approval is required. A librarian has been involved as consultant in developing the search strategy of the review, as well as experts were contacted for validating the search string. An article reporting findings of the review will be submitted to a peer-reviewed scientific journal with a dissemination aim. Dissemination will also involve the team to participate to national and international scientific conferences and to engage in other activities aimed at improving understanding of the phenomenon and stimulating new research.

3. Conclusion

The present scoping review will provide a comprehensive overview and detailed information about available evidence on cyberbullying related to ethnicity or indigeneity. These findings will inform researchers about aspects of the field that need further investigation. Moreover, results of the present work will be useful for professionals who work with children and adolescents, such as teachers, principals, school staff, psychologists, and will help parents to gain a better understanding of the phenomenon. Evidence from the present work will also be relevant for policymakers and NGOs working in the field.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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